

Appendix — RIPPLE: A Long-Sighted Self-Adaptation Approach to Retrain Machine Learning-Enabled Systems

This is the appendix for paper *RIPPLE: A Long-Sighted Self-Adaptation Approach to Retrain Machine Learning-Enabled Systems*, providing additional details on the experimental evaluation and results obtained. Specifically:

Section I provides an analysis of the importance of the top 5 features available for the LA-AIPs;

Section II analyzes RIPPLE’s latency when generating adaptation plans and its feasibility for online planning (**RQ.4**);

Section III investigates whether the cost of training LA-AIPs can be reduced by executing fewer model retrains during the AID construction process (**RQ.5**);

I. LA-AIP FEATURE IMPORTANCE

LA-AIP feature set. To select the features for the LA-AIPs to use, we started by (i) training the ST-AIPs with the three sets of features (small, medium, large) described in the original paper; and (ii) analyzing the feature importance of the top 5 features for each ST-AIP and feature set combination. Table I shows the top 5 most important features for the ST-AIPs as a function of the feature set (small, medium, large). We see that the top 5 features are fairly consistent regardless of the feature set. Based on this analysis, we selected the following features for the LA-AIPs: current TPR, current TNR and current fraud rate. These features correspond to approximately 90% of feature importance for most of the ST-AIPs that were tested.

II. FEASIBILITY FOR ONLINE PLANNING

Since RIPPLE aims to enable the online reasoning of when to retrain ML-enabled systems, we analyze the time complexity of the formal verification process (i.e., how long it takes to determine the next adaptation tactic to execute) as a function of the look-ahead. Table II reports these results and shows the average latency, and the 95-th and 99-th percentiles. We also report the size of the formal model (in terms of minimum and maximum number of states and number of transitions) as a function of the look-ahead.

Overall, the results shows that incrementing the look-ahead naturally leads to an increase of the latency to extract the adaptation strategy. However even for look-ahead 10 it takes on average less than 3 seconds to extract the adaptation strategy, and 3.51 seconds on the 99-th percentile. Thus, regarding **RQ.4** we verify that RIPPLE’s latency is fast enough for a large majority of non-safety-critical ML-enabled systems

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Fig. 1: Predictive quality of the *Root-LA-AIPs* in terms of MAE and PCC when decreasing the number of retrains employed to create the short-term AID. Due to space constraints, we show the plots only for *retrain*, however *nop Root-LA-AIPs* showed the same trends.

(e.g., fraud detection, machine translation, and recommendation systems).

III. COST OF TRAINING LA-AIPs

When creating LA-AIPs, the dominant cost is associated with building the AID, given that this entails performing multiple retrains of the ML model under adaptation. As such, we conduct a sensitivity analysis aimed at studying how reducing the number of *retrains* performed to build the AID impacts the predictive quality of the LA-AIPs.

Specifically, we sub-sample the AID at random to reduce the number of retrains used to gather information on ML retrain benefits. The resulting AID is then used to train the *Root-LA-*

TABLE I: Feature importance of the top 5 most important features for the random forest ST-AIPs.

Feature Set	Retrain-TPR		Nop-TPR		Retrain-TNR		Nop-TNR	
	Feature	Imp.	Feature	Imp.	Feature	Imp.	Feature	Imp.
Small	curr-TPR	66.47	curr-TNR	56.02	curr-TPR	47.16	curr-TNR	48.46
	curr_fraud_rate	28.74	curr_fraud_rate	39.88	curr_fraud_rate	38.16	curr_fraud_rate	40.22
	ratio_new_old_data	2.69	curr-TPR	3.15	ratio_new_old_data	9.61	curr-TPR	5.35
	curr-TNR	1.71	ratio_new_old_data	0.73	curr-TNR	3.78	ratio_new_old_data	4.17
	prev-TNR	0.2	prev-TPR	0.12	prev-TPR	0.66	prev-TNR	0.91
Medium	curr-TPR	65.46	curr-TNR	55.82	curr-TPR	46.25	curr-TNR	47.68
	curr_fraud_rate	26.14	curr_fraud_rate	36.89	curr_fraud_rate	33.05	curr_fraud_rate	37.38
	ratio_new_old_data	2.33	curr-TPR	2.34	ratio_new_old_data	9.05	curr-TPR	4.17
	curr_uncertainty_fraud	2.06	curr_uncertainty_fraud	2.27	curr_uncertainty_fraud	4.02	ratio_new_old_data	3.03
	curr-TNR	1.48	ratio_new_old_data	0.64	curr-TNR	2.75	curr_uncertainty_fraud	2.58
Large	curr-TPR	64.76	curr-TNR	55.49	curr-TPR	45.39	curr-TNR	46.91
	curr_fraud_rate	23.17	curr_fraud_rate	35.55	curr_fraud_rate	29.92	curr_fraud_rate	35.1
	curr_uncertainty_fraud	1.66	curr_uncertainty_fraud	2.02	ratio_new_old_data	7.69	curr-TPR	3.32
	ratio_new_old_data	1.52	curr-TPR	1.97	curr_uncertainty_fraud	3.21	curr_uncertainty_fraud	1.91
	curr-TNR	1.07	scores-JSD	0.41	curr-TNR	2.02	ratio_new_old_data	1.72

TABLE II: Latency of the adaptation strategy extraction process (in seconds) and model size as a function of the look-ahead. Note that look-ahead 1 corresponds to a myopic system.

	LA	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Avg ± stdev [s]		2.64	2.70	2.71	2.77	2.80	2.80	2.87	2.81	2.87	2.90
		±	±	±	±	±	±	±	±	±	±
		0.36	0.35	0.38	0.39	0.41	0.41	0.38	0.44	0.42	0.40
95-perc [s]		3.13	3.15	3.25	3.29	3.31	3.32	3.35	3.37	3.41	3.42
99-perc [s]		3.20	3.22	3.32	3.36	3.37	3.39	3.43	3.44	3.49	3.51
Num (min) states (max)		13	62	194	303	444	582	720	841	985	1081
			77	336	524	710	917	1138	1352	1587	1837
Num (min) transitions (max)		14	70	229	347	503	644	791	921	1074	1250
			88	402	622	835	1074	1329	1574	1836	2125

AIPs, which are evaluated on the full test-set. Each sub-sample percentage is repeated 10 times for reliability. The results are depicted in Figure 1, which shows that the performance of the LA-AIPs remains largely unaltered when using up to 30% smaller AIDs. As such, for **RQ.5** we conclude that *the cost benefits enabled by RIPPLE (Figure 4 of the main manuscript) can be achieved by performing just one third of the ML model retrains used to build the AIDs considered in this paper.*